

Food As An Ingredient Of Well-Being: From Food And Well-Being To Food Well-Being (FWB): A Consumer Perspective

Asim Shabir, Veronique Cova, Ubedullah Khoso, Qasim Ali Shah

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Abstract

This cross-cultural, qualitative research has provided new insight into consumer perceptions of food well-being. Our findings suggest that well-being is a broad concept in which food is an ingredient. Food and well-being share various common elements, and food well-being can be defined as an individual's psychological, physical, social, and societal relationship with food ascribed by our affordability and food literacy. Pleasure, sharing, and respect emerged as three interesting dimensions of food well-being that could be used to transform consumer behavior in respect of reducing overconsumption, food waste, and hunger in society. The authors explored dimensions of well-being and food for both countries of study to understand their cultural differences, and to explain how food influences well-being. The authors' findings may help consumers, public policymakers, and marketers reinvest implications and values into consumers' association with food.

Introduction

We eat food not only to meet the basic nutritional requirements of our bodies but also to meet physical, social, and psychological nourishment, as food has become a source of pleasure, happiness, love, sharing, and belonging. But in today's rapidly changing lifestyles, we are caught out by the Food myopia, which results in immediate gratification, whilst ignoring the long-term consequences of food consumption (Qazi and Cova, 2019). The Consumers' association with food is not only limited to health, but it involves several other food associations whom we call Well-being (WB) (Block *et al.*, 2011).

Pakistani consumers spend almost half of their income on food (World Economic Forum, 2016); however, the food consumption norms in the country are alarming and require a transformation. For instance, according to a study in *The Lancet* medical journal, Pakistan is the ninth most obese country in the world (Marie Ng *et al.*, 2014), encompassing 21% men and 26% women as obese respectively. There may be plenty of reasons behind such statistics, though it will have much to do with the eating behavior and consumption norms of the people there. An average Pakistani consumes three times more cooking oil per year (15 liters) than does the average Westerner (5 liters) (World Economic Forum, 2016). Fast food is preferred by 89% of Pakistanis, due to its palatability and convenience, although 70% believe it to be the probable cause of obesity (Baig and Saeed, 2012).

Statistics show that other Asian countries that have similar consumption norms also demonstrate these alarming obesity figures, i.e., China (28.3% of men and 27.4% of women) and India (19.5% of men and 20.7% of women) rank second and third respectively in terms of obesity after the USA (70.9% of men and 61.9% of women) (WHO, 2014). Similarly, Europe is placed second globally with an average obesity prevalence level of 15.9% across EU member states (Eurostat, 2016) and obesity is considered a major health problem in Europe (WHO, 2018). According to OECD (2017), 23.8% Male and 24% of females are obese in France, this must also be related to food consumption norms of French as according to (Rozin, 2005), French people eat food for pleasure. Nevertheless, obesity figures in France are increasing and are expected to increase by 21% in 2030 (OECD, 2017).

Looking at current consumption norms and the medicalized approach toward health, the authors are proposing a shift from viewing food as 'health' to viewing food as 'well-being', as proposed by (Block *et al.*, 2011). However, this will require a transformation in our attitudes and behaviors toward food from food as health to food as well-being. Such a transformation is on the agenda of transformative consumer research (TCR), to identify the problems faced by consumers and society and propose transformative solutions in pursuit of well-being (Mick *et al.*, 2012) and to come up with alternative food consumption patterns to be applied to consumer food behaviors since food affects our well-being in various ways (Ares *et al.*, 2015).

However, the literature concerning well-being lacks consensus on its definition and construct (McMahon *et al.*, 2010) and the theory-based formulations of well-being are still lacking; as a result, various scholars have tried to clarify the perceived meaning of 'well-being' for consumers (Dodge *et al.*, 2012a; Forgeard *et al.*, 2011) but no one has given any explicit definition (Mick, 2008; Ozanne and Saatcioglu, 2008). Wellbeing is not even defined in other foundational Transformative Consumer research studies (Bazerman, 2001), particularly in fields such as macro marketing (Wilkie and Moore, 2006), social marketing (Andreasen, 2002), and quality of life marketing (Lee and Sirgy, 2004).

Perception of wellbeing among consumer societies is strongly influenced by their income level and culture (Cummins, 2000; Diener *et al.*, 2003). Additionally, consumers belonging to various cultures possess diverse values and are exposed to numerous socio-economic situations; hence, they have contrasting criteria for evaluating well-being (Diener and Suh, 2000). Literature suggests that, in most empirical studies that concern well-being, incorporation of a cultural element is still lacking (Diener and Ryan, 2009; Meiselman, 2013). However, Cultural context is relevant, and the notion of food wellbeing may not be transferable to other cultures because consumption patterns vary as per the culture and hence it's vital to extend the FWB spectrum in international settings by focusing on the antecedents, processes, and consequences of Food Well-being (Mugel *et al.*, 2019).

Most of the research on food and well-being perceptions has been conducted in individualistic cultures (US and France), therefore, understanding and comparing the way people from collectivist cultures (Pakistan) define and associate themselves with food and well-being will be a useful value addition to the previous literature as it will help in incorporating cultural element into the notion of wellbeing and also exploring the contrasting criteria that consumers from a developed and developing countries have towards wellbeing. Moreover, understanding how food and well-being are related will provide all-inclusive knowledge about our perceptions of food products, which will help marketers and policymakers to predict consumer consumption but also consider their well-being in the long term (Boelsma *et al.*, 2010). Therefore, this study has three-fold goals, first to identify and compare how Pakistani and French consumers perceive well-being. Second, how do these both countries relate to food, and third, how do they associate food with wellbeing?

The rest of the article is structured as follows. First, the review of the literature is presented followed by methodology, findings, and discussion. Finally, the conclusion and implications for both theory and practice are presented.

The Definition of Well-being (WB)

Well-being is one of the ultimate end-state conditions that people pursue to achieve a good life (Diener *et al.*, 2003). From a theoretical point of view, well-being represents what is good for an individual and therefore it has been argued that our choices and lifestyle decisions are oriented towards achieving well-being (Angner, 2009). WB has significant implications for our behavior and other functional spheres of life (Ryan and Deci, 2001a). It is a relevant concept in various disciplines, such as psychology, economics, and sociology (de Chavez *et al.*, 2005). In a layperson's language, wellbeing denotes optimal functioning and experience (Ryan and Deci, 2001a). However, the exact nature of such an optimal functioning is yet to be clearly defined because many Psychologists and Philosophers have conceptualized the notion of wellbeing differently. The concept of well-being revolves around the philosophies of hedonism; where well-being is based on our subjective happiness, and it is linked to various positive and negative facets of life (Diener *et al.*, 1999) and eudemonism which takes account of self-actualization of human potential for growth (Fromm, 1947).

Both these approaches to well-being are further differentiated, based on their dependence on subjective and objective measures to define wellness. Hedonic Psychologist states that consumers' well-being is based on an individual's subjective happiness and is concerned about various good, bad, pleasurable, and displeasure able dimensions of life. Therefore, happiness is not only limited to physical hedonism, rather it can also be extracted from a variety of other crucial consequences such as goal fulfillment (Diener *et al.*, 1999). In comparison, the eudemonic approach to well-being is more objective, as it requires meeting certain needs, which are ingrained in the nature of all humans and whose apprehension is favorable for their growth (Fromm, 1947). The extent to which consumers define the term well-being carries significant implications with itself, as it has a substantial influence on their behaviors and various functional domains of life, mainly, concerned with the experiences of well-being (Ryan and Deci, 2001b).

The notion of well-being comprises of various dimensions such as physical, intellectual, social, emotional, occupational, spiritual, economic, environmental, political, Life appreciation, and also psychological aspects (positive moods and emotions) (Ares *et al.*, 2015; Veenhoven, 2000). Based on the complexity and lack of consensus on the meaning and definition of wellbeing, it is essential to comprehend, how consumers conceptualize the notion of wellbeing, precisely, in a food context, and how consumers perceive food to affect their wellbeing (Diener and Ryan, 2009; Meiselman, 2013).

Consumer Associations with Food

People often consider food as a source of enhancing health; however, food is not just a matter of nutrition rather, it is a symbol, myth, and expression of identity (Atkins and Bowler, 2001). Food, being a cultural component is a social vehicle to form social relationships and distinctions also influence consumers' food choices (Rozin, 2005). The way we, as consumers, associate food products and their consumption is a significant aspect of our postmodern consumer due to the shift of our food choices and pattern of consumption as per our lifestyles and identities (Firat and Venkatesh, 1995).

Food is perceived differently in different cultures: for some, food sustains and improves health and is considered to be a source of survival. For others, food is a source of socialization and pleasure (Rozin, 2005). Research indicates that consumers, in European markets, consider food as a source of health and are more interested in healthy-eating campaigns as they relate it with their well-being (Rudawska, 2001). German and Scottish consumers preferred a healthy diet and wanted their food to be as natural as possible, like fruits and vegetables, whereas Italian and Spanish consumers prefer a healthy diet based on balance and variety (Synnott *et al.*, 2007). Moreover, French consumers eat for pleasure as well as health, avoid snacking, enjoy high-quality food at mealtimes in moderate quantity and do more exercise unlike their American counterparts (Rozin, 2005), however, no such study exists considering Pakistani consumers which further to the importance of this study being conducted in Pakistan and comparing it to a country like France where consumers are more concerned about their food choices and health.

Food and Well-being

Food is related to well-being in a variety of ways, owing to its multidimensional nature. Firstly, it tends to influence our physical health and body functioning; secondly, it has a psychological influence on our behavioral and cognitive functioning (Bellisle *et al.*, 1998; Dye and Blundell, 2002; Gibson and Green, 2002). Furthermore, food provides more than basic nutrients; it serves various functions of our lives. Food has symbolic, aesthetic, social, and moral implications and affects our appreciation of life by influencing mood and emotions, as well as global life judgments and social relationships; it also has the power to influence our life satisfaction by harming health (Macht, 2008; Rozin, 2005). Food tends to affect our Subjective wellbeing (Schnettler *et al.*, 2013) in four ways: positive emotions, negative emotions, global life judgments, and domain satisfaction (Diener *et al.*, 2003), and has a significant impact on our emotions (Canetti *et al.*, 2002; Macht, 2008). Moreover, food also influences well-being from a social perspective, as (Schnettler *et al.*, 2013) stated that those who dine with their families and eating healthy foods are satisfied with their food and life in general. However, this research will shed some more light on how food is associated with wellbeing by comparing two countries having significant socioeconomic and cultural differences.

Methodology

We spoke to 30 people (15 French and 15 Pakistani) between the ages of 24 and 35, who we interviewed individually at their homes or another private location. Respondent profiles are shown in the Appendices. We chose a convenience as well as snow bowling sampling technique (Creswell, 2013). Moreover, we used three qualitative techniques (using a direct and indirect approach) to explore consumer perceptions of well-being, food, and food well-being: word association, photo-elicitation technique-based interviewing, and open-ended questions (Ares *et al.*, 2015; Loeffler, 2004; Mugel *et al.*, 2019; Roininen *et al.*, 2006).

These techniques involve tasks that are less structured than quantitative approaches, and, therefore, allow deeper probing of consumers' behavior (Lawless and Heymann, 2010). We chose word association because it allows an indirect approach to identify consumers' spontaneous associations with well-being in a food-specific context, as well as a general context (Steinman, 2009).

We sourced photographs on Google based on well-being and food-related keywords that had been used in previous research and we selected the final images with the help of a qualitative research expert in visual methods. (Lachal *et al.*, 2012) also used photo-elicitation to understand the role of food in the family lives of obese teenagers. Using images as a stimulus to elicit information from participants whereby the image is produced by someone other than the research participants helps them to express their feeling and beliefs (Petermans *et al.*, 2014). Asking an individual to talk about a particular image is an attempt to get that person to associate themselves with the photo and whatever it characterizes (Leppert, 1996). That is why we decided to use photographs to encourage the participants to associate themselves with the photos based on their own life experiences, which are close to their perception of well-being and food associations in various settings.

The interview was carried out in two parts: first, the word association and open-ended questions, i.e., questions numbered 1, 3, and 5. Second, respondents were given a questionnaire that included colored photos and

questions (2 and 4). We asked participants to read the questions and look at the pictures for three minutes and then to select the pictures on a priority basis. We then asked them the reasons for their choice.

Results and Discussion

For the analysis, we categorized the data via thematic analysis. We generated comparisons between the coded reports to identify the emerging themes and being carried out separately to identify and compare the cultural differences between the respondents of two countries. The thematic analysis is a four-step process that creates codes, concepts, and themes (Attride-Stirling, 2001), which are related, in our case, to consumers' perception of well-being. This technique allowed us to identify the common issues or words in the text, which resulted in the emergence of themes based on the frequency of ideas or words (Owen, 1984).

Perceptions of Well-being

Based on word association and the photo-elicitation-technique based questions, when respondents were asked to choose 5 photos out of the 20 shown to them that best illustrated their perception of well-being, the most frequently mentioned words were Happiness (n=83), Money (n=43), Health (n=41), Family (n=32), and Success (n=26) combining data from both countries. Happiness was the most salient association to well-being by participants from both countries, though Pakistani participants paid more relevance to Money (n=43) and Family (n=32), compared to French participants who paid more attention to Health (n=41). Individual terms were gathered and categorized into six different themes based on the frequently occurring terms at the aggregate level, as shown in **Table 01**:

For participants in both countries, psychological aspects were the most prominent followed by social and physical aspects. The French linked well-being to physical aspects more often when compared to the Pakistanis, who were inclined more towards socializing.

Table 01: Well-being Associations

Codes	Themes	Frequency	
		Pakistan	France
Happiness, pleasure, satisfaction, joy, comfort, relaxation, fun	Psychological	80	72
Family, belonging, friends, sharing, celebration, secure, support.	Social	45	42
Health, nutrition, exercise, food, energy	Physical	40	47
Achievement, stress-free, team, reward, appreciation, creativity	Occupational	36	42
Contribution, peace, prosperity, freedom, equality, cooperation	Societal	35	32
Money, job, affordability, richness, wealth, resources, shopping	Economic	40	24

Another emerging theme was an occupational association. The French associated this theme slightly more with their well-being perception than the Pakistanis. One of the most exciting themes that emerged was a societal concern, as the participants from both countries wanted to contribute to society by bringing peace, freedom, and prosperity.

The participants of both countries described a variety of associations with well-being. This shows that there is no standard definition of well-being, and all of us have our interpretations of well-being, depending upon the country and culture we belong to and our specific circumstances. This result is in accord with previous literature that defines well-being as a multidimensional construct (Diener and Ryan, 2009; Diener and Suh, 2000; Dodge *et al.*, 2012b).

Psychological aspects were the most prominent associations for all the consumers, as shown in Table 1. This finding is also in agreement with (Statham and Chase, 2010), affirming, well-being is not only limited to physical aspects of life, instead it also comprises non-physical aspects. As with our case, participants expressed certain positive moods and emotions, the most significant being happiness, pleasure, satisfaction, joy, and comfort. Similar results have been found by (Diener and Ryan, 2009), stating that the key determinants of Subjective Wellbeing are those whereby consumers feel pleasant emotions and can ignore any unpleasant emotions.

Associating well-being with food and **health** was found to be very common among the consumers of both countries, as mentioned in Table 1. The food choices that we make affect our well-being (physical dimension). Food choices have an influence on the lives of consumers – positively (health, energy) as well as negatively

(obesity and other diseases) – which makes physical health a predominant part of an individual’s well-being (McMahon *et al.*, 2010).

Moreover, the participants also associated well-being with the **social aspects** of their lives, as the act of socializing enhances one’s ability to network and bond with others. This agrees with the findings of Lelkes (2006) that socializing with family and friends is positively associated with Subjective Well-being.

Besides, the respondents also described other dimensions of well-being such as **economic and occupational**, which refer to the global evaluation of life (Diener *et al.*, 2009). They have described a significant relationship between well-being and satisfaction in all other life domains.

Our findings suggest that the Pakistani consumers were less concerned about the health aspects of well-being, and economic aspects were not particularly prominent for French consumers. Understandably, Pakistan, as a developing country, has less per capita income than the French, so, consequently, the Pakistanis place more importance on economic aspects of well-being. The average income level strongly influences perceived well-being (Diener and Diener, 1995). Interestingly, both countries considered societal concern a part of well-being and described their willingness to contribute to society in every possible way to help bring about peace, prosperity, and equality. Such differences in associations of well-being can be attributed to socio-economic contexts, values, and cultural differences of both countries, and previous literature about well-being confirms such variations to be part of perceived general well-being (Diener *et al.*, 2003).

The next section addresses the second research question about consumers’ association with food, the meaning of food for themselves, and how they related to food.

Associations with Food

The following themes emerged, as shown in table 2.

Quest for survival

Respondents consider food as a necessity to survive, as it helps them meet their biological hunger and provides them with energy to perform all the physical and mental activities of their lives. Survival was a frequent association with food for both nationalities; however, the frequency was slightly higher among the Pakistani participants.

Food is more of a necessity for me, and I would eat it for the sake of living. I am blessed to have access to food compared to many others, who do not have (Respondent-Fr).

Food is the soul of life as everything starts and ends with food (Respondent-Pak)

Our finding of the quest for survival is per Saper *et al.*, (2002), stating food is a significant source of energy, and consuming food in adequate quantities is an obligation for all living beings to survive, as food ensures a balanced homeostatic mechanism in all climates.

Table 02: Food Associations

Codes	Themes
Necessity, hunger, physical need, primary need, survival	Survival
Taste, aroma, joy, happiness, pleasure, delight, enjoyment, satisfaction, treat Family, friends, belonging, sharing moments, conversations, gathering, celebration	Psychological Social
Healthy, nutrition, active mentally and physically, balanced, quality, body, life, energy, obesity, overconsumption, malnutrition, lack of nutrition	Physical
Sharing, cultural food, love, homemade, variety, neighbors	Societal

The physical aspect of food.

Respondents believe in eating healthily to stay in good shape mentally as well as physically. Fascinatingly, apart from food choice, consumption quantity is also an essential factor in staying healthy and active; thus, we need to know what and how much to eat.

I eat food to have energy and good health; you need to have a proper balance between what and how much you eat, but it should be healthy to stay in good shape (Respondent-Fr).

Both the French and Pakistani respondents equally believed that excess in any way is bad, and over-consumption, under-consumption, and lack of food knowledge can be detrimental to our health; however, the French were considerably more health conscious compared to the Pakistani consumers. Research indicates that consumers, especially in European markets, are more concerned with and interested in healthy-eating campaigns because eating healthily has physical and mental benefits (Rudawska, 2001). Cook (2007) states

that food should not be considered just as a commodity to eat and live, instead we should focus on eating well to flourish, as food is a useful way for us to reward ourselves for our power struggles.

Psychological aspects of food.

Food is a pleasure for me; people take time to eat and enjoy eating excellent meals which are healthy at the same time, but, for some, taste comes before hygiene (Respondent-Fr).

I give more priority to the taste and pleasure in food, food must be hygienic and tasty also but for me, taste comes before hygiene (Respondent-Pak)

Respondents showed the most pleasure orientation toward food, as eating tasty food makes them happy, and it is not only a source of health but also a source of fun and enjoyment. Interestingly, French consumers were not focusing simply on the palatability of food but wished it to be healthy, though the Pakistanis give more importance to pleasure.

The way that participants revealed their positive moods and actions can be referred to as the hedonic characteristics of food consumption, and all of these are the main elements of consumer food choice (Lawless and Heymann, 2010). Moreover, such food-based emotions are pertinent for determining our food preferences (Macht, 2008).

Quest for socializing

Most respondents stated that they love to both eat out and eat at home with their friends and family, share their special moments, and spend time together.

Food might be a tool to gather friends, family, colleagues to exchange everything, so this is one of the main reasons that I go out eating – to have someone with me and have conversations (Respondent-Fr).

Furthermore, food becomes an excuse to meet with friends and spend some quality time. The food serves the purpose of socializing, consumers nurture their social relationships via food, and family bonding is strengthened among many cultures by the rituals of eating together especially in various collectivist cultures as the whole family sits together to eat and to celebrate special occasions (Bublitz *et al.*, 2011; Motley and Perry, 2009).

Societal association with food

Food is also a symbol of love, care, and respect. Through the love of sharing one's food with friends, family, neighbors, and especially with those who have little access to food, we can show our care towards people and earn respect at the same time.

If you share the food with your neighbors and friends, it gives you respect. It also provides respect, love, and affection to others (Respondent-Pak).

Food is not just a matter of nutrition, but also a symbol, myth, and an expression of identity (Atkins and Bowler, 2001). The sharing of food is an exchange or barter (Belk, 2010); however, the sharing of food to gain respect brings new insight to the literature surrounding food symbolism. Surprisingly, this theme emerged only in the case of Pakistan. This is perhaps due to cultural differences, as Pakistan belongs to a collectivist country domain whereas France is an individualistic nation.

It is quite interesting to highlight that many participants referred to food while thinking about well-being.

Food comes to my mind whenever I think about well-being. Food is part of well-being, well-being is a broader concept, and food is one of its ingredients (Respondent-Pak).

This demonstrates that not only is food strongly associated with well-being but also it is considered a fundamental part of it. Interestingly, participants mentioned the word 'food' more than 200 times while defining well-being, so here lies clear evidence of a link between well-being and food. We can compare Table 1 with Table 2 to see that the themes that emerged in the form of well-being and food are almost the same, and they both overlap with each other, **excepting occupational dimensions of well-being and the survival dimension of food**, as shown in Figure 01.

This overlap between the dimensions of well-being and food confirms our next research question of consumer perception of food and well-being as a single concept or measure; in other words – how does food affect our well-being? The findings are discussed below.

Consumer Perception of Food Well-being

As researchers, we hold three theories: 1) the French and Pakistani consumers share the same associations with regards to general well-being, 2) they share the same associations with food in general, and 3) food influences the well-being of both nationalities. Our findings justify our propositions. Consumers of both countries have almost the same associations with food and well-being, there being only slight differences in the priority that is given to some of the food and well-being dimensions.

The themes noted in Figure 01 represent multiple aspects of food well-being. Interestingly the themes that appear here are almost the same as the well-being and food associations mentioned in Table 1 and Table 2, although we did encounter one additional theme, that of food literacy.

Figure 01: Food Well-being Synthesis

Psychological aspects

Food and well-being have a psychological association.

I feel more relaxed by eating the food I like the most; it refreshes me and makes me feel happier and the pleasure that I feel while consuming tasty food such as a pastry or a big bar of chocolate is amazing. In short, having access to such yummy food is well-being for me (Respondent-Pak).

Participants of both countries defined food well-being from a psychological perspective, they believed that food influences their emotions (pleasure and happiness), which are not distinct from well-being.

Psychological Aspect of Food Wellbeing is ranked equally by the French and Pakistani consumers. Food-related emotions contribute significantly to the well-being of an individual (King *et al.*, 2012). Consumers often give more importance to pleasure, as they seek sensory experience from eating (Gottfried, 2010). Moreover, consumer well-being is also revealed via consumers' focus on food and the pleasure they experience while consuming (Mugel *et al.*, 2019).

Social aspects.

Socializing is a common factor that defines food and well-being. As participants mentioned, food is a source of sharing good moments and experiences with family and friends.

I get to make many friends over food. When we exchange conversations about cultures, we often discuss what we eat, why so many spices, this is one of the subjects we talk about, and this subject allows me to make more friends (Respondent-Pak).

Moreover, gatherings arranged around a food table give people the opportunity to make new friends, understand new cultures, and, at the same time, have fun.

Socialization was another food well-being dimension that arose from an individual's social relationship with food. This socialization process begins in childhood, especially as the family is a crucial part of the learning process, and parents teach their children the food consumption norms of what, how, and how much to eat (Cavanagh *et al.*, 2014; Moore *et al.*, 2002). Media and marketing also serve as socializing agents (Harris *et al.*, 2009). For Pakistani consumers, food for socializing was comparatively more prominent than French consumers, which is probably due to the differences in food and cultural connections which are also learned through the process of socialization (Moschis, 1985).

Physical aspects

Respondents consider food as a crucial factor in the ability to remain healthy, energetic, and fit.

Many eat whatever they feel like eating, so in the process, they put on weight, where it causes risk for health. Eating well enhances your well-being and food bring health, which is linked with well-being (Respondent-Fr).

Participants also connected food and well-being from a **physical perspective**. For them, food well-being pertains also to their physical relationship with food. Pakistani consumers stated that there is some tradeoff between eating for pleasure and eating for health. This concurs with several studies, which claim that consumers do not willingly compromise sensory food pleasures for potential health benefits (Verbeke, 2006). This tradeoff is the obvious cause of poor eating habits and health-related problems in Pakistan, and leads to its inhabitants being overweight and, therefore, ranked ninth in the obesity index (Marie Ng *et al.*, 2014). Consequently, it is imperative to broaden the scope of food by considering other dimensions of well-being (as our findings also suggest that there are many other relationships that consumers have with food apart from health). Our relationship with food also defines our relationship with well-being as mentioned in Figure 01. For instance, the need for pleasure from food consumption leads consumers to enhance their caloric intake, as they start to focus more on the enjoyment aspect of food than on the health aspect (Mela, 2006), which negatively affects Wellbeing because poor food choices have a negative influence on health and overall well-being. Our findings suggest that food has a positive as well as a negative influence on our physical health; and our eating patterns, food knowledge, and affordability of food all have a part to play also. Hence, it's important to focus on food and wellbeing which help consumers develop healthy relationships with food (Block *et al.*, 2011).

Economic Aspects

Participants believe there is no free lunch; everything you buy has a price. All food costs money but buying healthy food costs more money.

Trying to eat healthily costs a lot; it's our own choice. If you want to eat healthily, you need to pay more (Respondent-Fr).

So, those people who have enough resources or money can easily afford healthy food such as organic or bio food whilst those who cannot afford these types of products don't buy them.

Block *et al.*, (2011) have also demonstrated an economic relationship with food, and they have emphasized the role of smaller, local merchants and of agricultural cooperatives in managing the availability of fresh fruit and vegetables as per consumer affordability and channel profitability. Interestingly, Pakistani consumers associated economic factors more with food and well-being, this is possible because of the economic difference between both countries and calls for the attention of the marketers and public policy makers in Pakistan to model the French practices relating to food safety and pricing policies.

Societal concern

Participants considered food to be a gift for every human being, though the unequal distribution and irresponsible behavior result in food waste. Some people starve, whilst others enjoy access to plenty of food.

When I don't waste food and eat appropriately, it makes me feel good that I do not miss using the given resources, which can be used by others who are deprived of it, so in some way, this also affects my wellbeing (Respondent-Pak).

It is the most thought-provoking food well-being dimension, as people of both countries explained food well-being based on their relationship with food in the form of sharing with others. Although the notion of sharing possessions such as households, income, and food (Belk, 2010) are not new in literature, as people have exchanged and bartered their possessions for many years, it has not, until now, been cited as a dimension for food well-being, particularly sharing without expecting anything in return.

This will be a healthy food well-being dimension to focus on future research, especially considering the alarming poverty, hunger, obesity, and food waste issues across the globe. This dimension was more prominent among Pakistani participants, probably because of the more resources and income disparity and the cultural differences between the two countries.

Food literacy Aspects

Participants commented on the food choices that have a positive and negative influence on their health.

One should eat various foods – like fruits and vegetables, fish, and meat as different foods are different sources of nutrition, knowing what and how much to eat is an essential characteristic of a person's well-being (Respondent-Fr).

They highlighted the importance of food knowledge, eating more fruit and vegetables and making mindful food choices, and avoid fatty burgers and oily foods that can result in health problems.

Lastly, one interesting finding concerned the role of food literacy in food well-being. We consider it a factor that can moderate an individual's food well-being. It is a multidimensional construct that includes autonomous food skills, contextualized practice of food knowledge, food learning process, and food language (Sumner, 2013). Participants of both countries emphasized the importance of food literacy and mentioned intrinsic food characteristics (such as nutrition, composition, calorie content, freshly made, or branded), and they highlighted some extrinsic aspects (like quality, price, and convenience). All these factors influence consumer food choices, food intake, and overall well-being (Chandon and Wansink, 2007; Wansink, 1996, 2004).

From our findings, we can infer that food influences various aspects of CWB, especially in terms of psychological, social, physical, and economic aspects of life, as shown in Figure 01. The findings of our present work are in concurrence with the following food well-being definition by Block et al. (2011): 'a positive psychological, physical, emotional, and social relationship with food at both the individual and society levels'. Our work broadens the scope of this definition by analyzing two countries that represent two different continents (Asia and Europe), and especially by including the societal dimension of food well-being in the form of sharing and respect, added as a new dimension to the existing definition. In nutshell, we observed significant cultural differences between both nationalities. Pakistani consumers gave more priority to psychological, social, and economic aspects of food and well-being, whereas French consumers focused more on psychological, social, and physical aspects.

Conclusion and Implications

The societal dimension is novel insight and provides a new direction to the concept of food wellbeing as it covers the respect for others and sharing of food. It will be interesting to see how sharing and respect contribute to the food wellbeing of consumers and mitigate the impact of overconsumption and food waste on the well-being of consumers in future studies. The current wellbeing dimensions will help marketers and public policymakers to design their offerings and policies to help consumers improve their WB, especially with regards to eating patterns and developing healthy food products having more consumer approval (Ares et al., 2015).

The Knowledge of all food well-being dimensions can help consumers to better understand their relationship with food and their eating habits not only in the context of eating healthy but also through the pleasure-driven from food experiences, socializing, and sharing the food with others around them (Mugel et al., 2019). Exactly how these food associations will continue to affect food well-being calls for future research, as researchers who are investigating food well-being need to consider how social, psychological, and health orientations towards food influence consumers' FWB. Moreover, it is also critical to consider the effect of socio-demographic discrepancies on consumer conceptualization of wellbeing.

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Author Information

Asim Shabir

Institute of Business Administration, Karachi
IBA Main Campus, KU

Veronique Cova

IAE Aix Marseille University, France
Pyuricard, Aix en Provence

Ubedullah Khoso

Iqra University
Defence View, Main Campus Karachi

Qasim Ali Shah

SZABIST Larkana
Szabist Larkana Campus, Sachal Colony
